

**METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING TECHNICAL
SCIENCES IN THE CONTEXT OF INNOVATIVE
EDUCATION**

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Annotation: This article provides information on the use of innovative technologies in universities in the process of teaching technical disciplines. Currently, at the present stage of the development of a modern student, it is very important that the student correctly perceives information in order to form skills, motivation, training and mastering technical disciplines. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education, article 14 on higher education says: higher education provides training for highly qualified specialists. The training of specialists with higher education is carried out in higher educational institutions (universities, academies, institutes and other educational institutions of higher education) based on secondary specialized, vocational education.

Keywords: future specialists, communication technologies, successful involvement

Scientific and technological progress and the external environment force modern enterprises to turn into increasingly complex systems that require professional specialists. The solution to these problems largely depends on the content and technology of training future specialists in the higher education system, and in particular the teaching of technical disciplines. The use of innovative technologies in technical disciplines allows you to select the necessary content and training tools in accordance with the program, modern production requirements and the chosen specialty.

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teaching of technical disciplines. The use of innovative technologies in technical disciplines allows you to select the necessary content and training tools in accordance with the program, modern production requirements and the chosen specialty. A modern teacher should be competent, know the latest achievements in education and technology, and be able to motivate students. To form the right direction of activity for students, to take into account the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of the individual. Recent advances in technology and science are bringing significant changes to the understanding of the role and ways of using information and communication technologies, which must be applied for the successful involvement of young people in the educational process and for an effective, really useful expansion of interest in the studied technical discipline. The use of technical means of learning (TSO) and interactive forms of learning in technical disciplines intensifies the transfer of information, expands illustrative material, creates problematic situations, organizes the student's search activity, strengthens the emotional background of learning, forms educational motivation, individualizes and differentiates the educational process.

The lecture acts as the leading link of the entire course of study and is a way of presenting voluminous theoretical material that ensures the integrity and completeness of its perception by listeners. When giving a lecture, it is advisable to conduct binary or web binary lectures with the participation of a lecturer and a highly qualified specialist from the production. Lectures with planned errors are very effective. This form of lecture organization attracts the attention of students throughout the lesson, as they have to look for mistakes by the teacher. It is also very important to use animation and video materials in lectures, when visually viewing the material, it is easier to digest. However, the lecture teaches you to passively perceive the material being studied. In order to avoid this, a direct dialogue between students and lecturers is effectively used, for example, in the format of a press conference. When conducting lectures on technical disciplines, to increase interest and assimilation of new material,

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circuits are set on LE 2I-NON-students in small groups should study the methodological material, assemble the circuits on physical layouts, take measurement results, plot the VAC and transfer characteristics of the elements, perform a virtual laboratory the work will compare the parameters of the diagrams and the graph.

Advantages of TCO in technical disciplines:

- 1) have a strong emotional impact;
- 2) allow you to show a process or phenomenon in its development, dynamics;
- 3) cause a variety of sensations (the world of sounds and colors);
- 4) provide a high emotional tone, and, as a rule, increased efficiency;
- 5) reduce the cost of the necessary training time.

The use of innovative teaching methods gives an effective result in the educational process. Innovative technologies in science and technology can be combined with each other. Each university teacher has more than 20-25 interactive teaching methods in their piggy bank when working with students. It is not necessary to know all the available interactive teaching methods. It is important to use the methods that the teacher most often uses using TSO.

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